

BETA FUNKTSIYASINING O'ZIGA XOS USULLARI

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Beta Funktsiyasi.

Beta funksiyasi, ehtimollik nazariyasi va statistikada muhim ahamiyatga ega. U beta taqsimotini ifodalashda qo`llaniladi, bu taqsimot esa o`zgaruvchilarning chegarali intervaldagi taqsimlanishiga asoslangan modellarni yaratishda qo`llanadi. Statistikada va genetika, molekulyar biologiya kabi sohalarda beta funksiyasi orqali optimallashtirish va parametrlarni baholash amalga oshiriladi.

Beta funksiyasi esa ikkita mustaqil o`zgaruvchiga ega bo`lib, quyidagicha ifodalanadi:

$$B(x, y) = \int_0^1 t^{x-1}(1-t)^{y-1} dt, \quad x > 0, y > 0 \quad (5)$$

xosmas integralga Eylerning Beta funksiyasi deyiladi. va nuqtalarga maxsus nuqtalar deyiladi.

(5) integralni ikkita integralning yig`indisi shaklida ifodalaymiz:

$$B(x, y) = \int_0^{\frac{1}{2}} t^{x-1}(1-t)^{y-1} dt + \int_{\frac{1}{2}}^1 t^{x-1}(1-t)^{y-1} dt,$$

bu yerda, Beta funksiya va da aniqlangan bo`lgani uchun, birinchi integral da, ikkinchi integral esa da yaqinlashuvchi bo`ladi.[1-10]

Beta funksiya xossalari.

1⁰. $B(x, y) = B(y, x)$; Haqiqatan $\tau = 1 - t$ deb o`zgaruvchini almashtirsak ,

$$B(x, y) = \int_0^1 t^{x-1}(1-t)^{y-1} dt = \int_0^1 \tau^{x-1}(1-\tau)^{y-1} dt = B(x, y).$$

2⁰. Bo`laklab integrallash usuli yordamida (5) formuladan, $y > 1$ bo`lganda $t^x = t^{x-1} - t^{x-1}(1-t)$ ayniyatni qo`llab, quyidagini hosil qilamiz:

$$\begin{aligned} B(x, y) &= \int_0^1 (1-t)^{y-1} d\left(\frac{t^x}{x}\right) = \frac{t^x(1-t)^{y-1}}{x} \Big|_0^1 + \frac{y-1}{x} \int_0^1 t^x(1-t)^{y-1} dt = \\ &= \frac{y-1}{x} \int_0^1 t^x(1-t)^{y-1} dt - \frac{y-1}{x} \int_0^1 t^x(1-t)^{y-2} dt = \end{aligned}$$

$$= \frac{y-1}{x} B(x, y-1) - \frac{y-1}{x} B(x, y).$$

Bundan

$$B(x, y) = \frac{y-1}{x+y-1} B(x, y-1), \quad x > 0, y > 1. \quad (6)$$

Bu formulani $y > 1$ bo'lganda uni kichiklashtirish maqsadida qo'llash mumkin; shunday qilib hamma vaqt ikkinchi argument 1 dan kichik yoki teng bo'lishiga erishish mumkin. Xuddi shunday birinchi argumentga nisbatan ham mulohaza yuritib, $x > 1$ da

$$B(x, y) = \frac{x-1}{y+x-1} B(x-1, y), \quad x > 1, y > 0. \quad (6')$$

(6) ga o'xshash keltirish formulasini olish mumkin. Agar natural son bo'lsa, (6) formulani qo'llab,

$$B(x, n) = \frac{n-1}{x+n-1} \cdot \frac{n-2}{x+n-2} \cdots \frac{1}{x+1} B(x, 1)$$

$B(x, 1) = \int_0^1 t^{x-1} dt = \frac{1}{x}$ ga ega bo'lamiz. Shuning uchun $B(x, n)$ uchun ham $B(n, x)$ uchun ham bir vaqtning o'zida

$$B(n, x) = B(x, n) = \frac{1 \cdot 2 \cdot 3 \cdot \dots \cdot (n-1)}{x \cdot (x+1) \cdot (x+2) \dots \cdot (x+n-1)} \quad (7)$$

ifodaga ega bo'lamiz.

Agar (7) da natural son m ga teng bo'lsa, u holda

$$B(m, n) = \frac{(n-1)!(m-1)!}{(m+n-1)!}$$

bo'ladi. [11-15]

3⁰. Agar (6) integralda $t = \frac{u}{u+1}$ almashtirib olsak, bu yerda u – yangi o'zgaruvchi 0 dan $+\infty$ gacha o'zgaradi, u holda quyidagi formula o'rinli:

$$B(x, y) = \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{u^{x-1}}{(1+u)^{x+y}} du. \quad (8)$$

4⁰. (6) formulada $0 < x < 1$ bo'lganda, $y=1-x$ deb olinsa,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{u+1} &= \sum_{k=0}^n (-1)^k u^k + (-1)^{n+1} \frac{u^{n+1}}{1+u} du = \int_0^1 \frac{u^{x+1} + u^x}{1+u} du = \\ &= (-1)^{n+1} \int_0^1 \frac{u}{u+1} (u^{x-1} + u^x) du + \sum_{k=0}^n (-1)^k u^k + \\ &+ (-1)^{n+1} \int_0^1 \frac{u^{n+1}}{u+1} \end{aligned}$$

ayniyatdan foydalanib,

$$B(x, 1-x) = \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{u^{x-1}}{1+u} du$$

$$= \int_0^1 \frac{u^{x-1} + u^{-x}}{1+u} du = (-1)^{n+1} \int_0^1 \frac{u}{1+u} (u^{x-1} + u^{-x}) du +$$

$$+ \sum_{k=0}^n (-1)^k \left(\frac{1}{k+x} + \frac{1}{k-x+1} \right) \quad (9)$$

ni olamiz:

$$0 \leq \int_0^1 \frac{u^{n+1}(u^{x-1} + u^{-x})}{1+u} du \leq \int_0^1 (u^{n+x} + u^{n+1-x}) du =$$

$$= \frac{1}{n+x+1} + \frac{1}{n+2-x}$$

bo'lgani uchun (9) formulada $n \rightarrow \infty$ deb limitga o'tilsa,

$$B(x, 1) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} (-1)^k \left(\frac{1}{x+k} + \frac{1}{k-x+1} \right)$$

$$= \frac{1}{x} + \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} (-1)^k \left(\frac{1}{x+k} + \frac{1}{x-k} \right) = \frac{\pi}{\sin \pi x}$$

ni hosil qilamiz. Oxirgi formula $\frac{1}{\sin z}$ funksiyaning elementlar kasrlarga yoyilmasidan

$z = \pi x$ bo'lganda hosil qilinadi. Demak quyidagi

$$B(x, 1-x) = \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{u^{x-1}}{(1+u)} du = \frac{\pi}{\sin \pi x}, \quad (0 < x < 1) \quad (10)$$

Formula o'rinli. Xususiyl holda, agar $x=1-x=\frac{1}{2}$ deb olinsa, u holda

$$B\left(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}\right) = \pi \quad (25')$$

Qiymatini olamiz.[1-15]

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